

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND COPING AMONG NURSING STAFF - A CROSS SECTIONAL WORKPLACE SURVEY FROM A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: Psychological disorders are projected to be among the top fourth leading causes of disability in the future. Nurses regularly face distressing situations in the workplace so it is important to know the psychological well-being among nursing staff. **Aim:** The present survey was therefore conducted to find out the level and different sources of workplace stress among nursing staff. **Methods:** The present survey included 132 female staff nurses working in different departments of hospital during 2013. Stratified random sampling technique was used. Four nurses were selected randomly from all the major departments of the hospital, two nurses from day shift and another two from the evening shift. **Results:** Out of total, majority (68%) was serving as full time whereas 32% were working on contract basis. The mean working hours in a week were 52.47 ± 7.23 hrs. On the scale of mental well being, the mean score for State of mind, Occupational well being and Confidence level were 10.38 ± 4.57 , 10.56 ± 3.21 and 8.92 ± 4.01 . These scores were more than their corresponding standard scores; 20.67, 14.28 and 10.37 respectively. Similarly the mean score for Quality of life and Energy Level were 7.22 ± 3.01 and 10.27 ± 2.86 . The standard score on these subscales are 12.73 and 14.95 respectively. **Conclusion:** The findings of the study indicate that improved organizational culture alone would trim down the rising levels of workplace stress as roots of existing workplace stress are not emerging from personal or the monitory factors.

Key words: Workplace stress, nurses, hospital, staff.

INTRODUCTION

Everyone experiences stress. It is a natural reaction that everyone experiences at one time or the other. It is a part of human nature. Stress is the body's response to

danger or perceived threat. It can serve as a driving

force in terms of obtaining results, but on the other hand, non-stop stress can act as a killer in terms of performance.^{1,2} Occupational stress is any discomfort which is felt and perceived at a personal level and triggered by instances, events or

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situations that are too intense and frequent in nature so as to exceed a person's coping capabilities and resources to handle them adequately.³

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimate that stress-related disorders will be one of the leading causes of disability by the Year 2020.⁴

Nursing profession requires gentleness, compassion and sensitivity. A nurse is a healthcare professional, who is responsible for the treatment, safety, and recovery of ill or injured people, health maintenance of the healthy, and treatment of life-threatening emergencies in a wide range of health care settings. In recent years there is a growing appreciation of the workplace stress.⁵⁻⁷

Nursing duties are manifold and cover a wide range of functions and responsibilities that depends with the level of qualification and the working environment. Nurses regularly face multiple, complex and distressing situations and encounter intense interpersonal and inter-professional problems and conflict in the workplace while trying to make appropriate and safe decisions.⁸

It is important to know the level of psychological distress and psychological well-being among nursing staff order to ensure a better health care delivery service. As psychological disorders are projected to be among the top fourth leading causes of disability in the future, research of its effects and association among those who are expected to be future professional mental and health provider would be useful. The present survey was therefore conducted to find out the level and different sources of workplace stress among nursing staff at a tertiary care teaching hospital in Haryana.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present cross sectional survey was conducted during March to September 2013 at a tertiary care teaching hospital in rural Haryana. Sampling frame was obtained from nursing superintendent. All the female staff nurses available in the wards and various outpatient departments at the time of interview were included in the study. Thus one hundred and thirty two female staff nurses, serving in the morning and evening shifts of various departments of a tertiary care facility were recruited. The stratified random sampling was adopted to include nurses working in various departments of hospital. Four nurses were selected randomly from all the major departments of the hospital, two nurses from day shift and another two from the evening shift. Male nursing staff was not included in the study.

Workplace stress was assessed by modified Williams and Cooper's (1998) Pressure Management Indicator. Pressure Management Indicator was developed by Williams and Cooper (1998) from the Occupational Stress Indicator developed by Cooper, Sloan & Williams in 1988 in order to address shortcomings in some scales of the Occupational Stress Indicator. The Pressure Management Indicator is a 120 item self-report measure, with 8 subscales as well as a demographic sheet. Pressure Management Indicator contains 12, 9, 40, 17 items in the areas of Mental Well-being, Physical Well-being, Sources of Pressure and Coping & Interpersonal Support mechanisms.

Study subjects were given a brief introduction about the purpose of the survey and then questionnaires were handed out to them. The questionnaires were distributed by authors in the wards and various outpatient departments himself. A brief orientation was given to each selected participant about the study tool. Informed consent was obtained. Each

participant took approximately 30 minutes to give their response. Forms were revised for completeness and consistency. Data entry, data checking and data analysis were done with the program SPSS (Statistical package for social science) version 17.0.5. Interpretation of the collected data was done by using appropriate statistical methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of one hundred and thirty two study subjects were included in the study. Out of total, ninety eight participants returned the filled proformas giving a response rate of 74.24%. Twelve proformas were not included in the analysis as they were not completely filled. Majority (47%) of them had duration of current job for 1-10 years. Thirty five percent of staff nurses worked for last 11-20 years and 18% of them had been working for more than 21 years.

Mean age of study participants was 33.5 ± 8.2 years. Mean working hours in a week were 52.47 ± 7.23 hours. The majority of the study subjects (68%) were working on fulltime basis whereas remaining (32%) were working on contract basis.

Calculated mean score for "Occupational well-being" which refers to how calm a person feels in terms of tension or other uncomfortable sensations at her workplace was 10.56 whereas the standard score on this subscale is 14.28. Energy level of the participants refers to the amount of energy and vitality someone has before he/she feels tired. Mean scores for all the dimensions of well-being were found to be less than their corresponding normative score level. (Table 1)

Table 1: Distribution of normative and mean scores for various dimensions of well-being

Dimensions of well-being	Normative Score	Mean	Standard deviation
State of mind	20.67	10.38	± 4.57
Confidence level	10.37	8.92	± 4.01
Physical well-being	14.95	9.75	± 3.72
Occupational well-being	14.28	10.56	± 3.21
Quality of life	12.73	7.22	± 3.01
Energy level	14.95	10.27	± 2.86
Resilience	17.66	9.43	± 3.53

The assessment of mental health of nurses has generally been ignored. The mental health of the health care providers has been assessed less commonly than their physical health by several researchers and this trend is prevalent across the globe. Fewer years of experience, negative family and friend support, and negative total work satisfaction were found to be significant predictors of psychological ill health among Egyptian nurses.⁹ Assessment of the mental health showed that majority were anxious and seem upset.

The physical health parameters showed lower than the corresponding normative score indicating that the study subjects may have some feeling of physical distress. On the other hand, medical examination of faculty which is done on yearly basis does not reveal any gross finding. Thus it can be said that possibility of underlying deteriorating mental health expressing in the form of somatic presentation i.e. tiredness cannot be ruled out and one need to keep in mind.

Mean scores of all the sources of the pressure in the staff nurses i.e. workload, relationships, recognition, organizational

climate, personal responsibility, managerial role, home/ work balance and daily hassles etc were found to be higher than their corresponding normative scores

except mean score of “conflict with supervisor” which was found to be almost equal to its corresponding normative score. (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of normative and mean scores for various sources of pressure

Sources of Pressure	Normative Score	Mean	Standard deviation
Workload	17.79	26.18	± 6.25
Torture of the higher authorities	15.24	24.41	± 6.82
Relationships	25.46	28.22	± 6.41
Shift problems	14.81	15.15	± 5.02
Recognition	12.49	14.56	± 3.58
Organizational climate	13.02	15.88	± 3.15
Personal responsibility	12.26	16.32	± 3.67
Managerial role	9.54	10.56	± 2.96
Lack of security in the work	10.36	12.84	± 4.03
Home/ work balance	13.92	16.74	± 4.91
Daily hassles	11.41	12.08	± 3.43
Conflict with supervisor	12.85	12.92	± 2.41

Another study from Coimbatore also revealed “Torture of the higher authorities” (52.8%) and “conflict with supervisor” (48.0%) as two most important sources of stress.¹⁰ Authors from other Asian countries also reported similar findings.¹¹

Lambert et al. also identified factors that influence and/or predict nurses level of well being, either physically or psychologically. Some of these factors include the likelihood to leave the current nursing position, lack of support, use of escape-avoidance as a coping mechanism, age, conflict with physicians and conflict with other nurses psychological hardiness, lack of emphatic concern and poor communication self esteem and social intimacy, work family conflict, confidence in one’s ability and use of self control and distancing as coping methods.¹²

Coping mechanisms and interpersonal support mechanisms were also assessed. Scores for problem focus, life / work balance and social Support were calculated. Problem focus means the

extent to which one plans ahead and manages his/her time to deal with problems. Life/work balance means extent to which a person is able to separate home from work and not let things get to him/her. Mean scores were higher than their corresponding normative scores in above two coping mechanisms. Social support refers to the help one gets by discussing problems or situations with other people. Mean score was nearly equal to normative score.

Table 3: Distribution of normative and mean scores for various Coping and interpersonal support mechanisms.

Coping and interpersonal support	Normative Score	Mean	Standard deviation
Problem focus	24.52	26.14	± 3.43
Social Support	10.75	12.22	± 2.05

Life/Work balance	16.90	16.38	± 2.58
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Another study from Thailand conducted among Thai nurses observed that nurses having more experience used more of positive methods of coping like listening to music, reading, talking with the partner or a colleague and walking to cope with stress.¹³

Australian nurses used following coping strategies or mechanisms to cope up piled up stress - seeking support, problem solving and self-control whereas stressors included work overload, role conflicts and experiences of aggression.¹⁴ Flanagan stated that the influence of organizational decision making strategies, staff support systems, and employee unions on job satisfaction and stress might provide further information about intent to stay and turnover and also found that the job stress was a significant predictor of job satisfaction.¹⁵

CONCLUSION

The study highlights fact that nurses serving at a tertiary care hospital experienced higher levels of workplace stress which in turn lessen their professional capabilities. Improved organizational culture alone would trim down the rising levels of workplace stress as roots of existing workplace stress are not emerging from personal or the monitory factors.

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